

PELAGIC ECOSYSTEMS OF THE SOUTHERN OCEAN

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The pelagic ecosystems of the Southern Ocean (Antarctic bioregion) are the main component of the entire Antarctic ecosystem. They are complex biological systems consisting of populations of individual species in dynamic equilibrium and stability. The pelagic zone of the Southern Ocean has huge biological productivity based on the peculiarities of oceanographic parameters characterized by constancy in time and space: the Antarctic Circumpolar Current, the ice continent, and the winter ice cover of the ocean. These parameters provide vertical water exchange and a constant supply of biogenic elements to the surface. The pelagic zone of the Southern Ocean can be divided into several main components: the Subantarctic (SA), the high-latitude Antarctic (HA), the shelf and slope of the Antarctic continent – the continental seas (HS), the islands (including seamounts under topographic influence) (IP), the mesopelagic (MP). Each component has its own unique species composition, as is known, more than 90% of endemism.

Currently available scientific data on biology, oceanography of the Southern Ocean, and statistics on the fishing (and observation) of biological resources by humans allow us to determine for each of the above-proposed components of the pelagic ecosystem of the Southern Ocean the main species (groups of species) – biological markers:

SA - *Electrona carlsbergi*, *Themisto gaudichaudi*;

HA - *Euphausia superba*, *Electrona antarctica*, *Balaenoptera* spp.;

HS - *Euphausia superba*, *Euphausia crystallorophias*, *Pleuragramma antarcticum*, all species of fish of the family Nototheniidae, *Balaenoptera* spp.;

IP - All plankton accumulated by hydrodynamic circulation around islands and above underwater elevations due to the effect of "Tylor's columns";

MP - Copepoda, Bathylagidae, Gonostomatidae, Bathylagidae, *Protomyctophum* spp., Oegopsida.

The difficulties of obtaining scientific data in the Southern Ocean, known to all researchers, do not allow us to assess the entire ecosystem in winter. The high cost of research is reflected in the spatial coverage of the research: most areas of the Southern Ocean have never been visited by scientists, and the research was carried out fragmentarily, sometimes repeating itself after several decades. New technologies (especially underwater video observations) have brought us very interesting data on the animal world of the Southern Ocean, including the biomass and distribution of pelagic inhabitants. Underwater cameras installed on the fishing gear of Ukrainian fishing vessels for the first time captured the spawning of the pelagic squid *Slosarczykovia circumantarctica* at depths of 1,100 meters in the Weddell Sea, feeding at the bottom at depths of 800–2,500 meters *Euphausia superba*, and mass spawning of the pelagic fish *Notolepis coatsi*.